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DESCRIPTION OF A NEW ACANTHOCYBIUM FROM THE
PHILIPPINE ISLANDS.

By ALVIN SEALE.

(From the Ichthyological Section, Biological Laboratory, Bureau of
Science, Manila, P. I.)

Acanthocybium forbesi Seale sp. nov. Forbes' Kingfish. (Plate I.¹)

Head 4 in length without caudal; depth 7.3; eye 10 in head, 5 in snout; dorsal XXVI 1119, 9; anal II 10, 8. The lateral line has its origin considerably above the opercles and is strongly curved under the 14-17 dorsal spines. In the posterior portion of its course the line is wavy. Between the strong curve of the line and the caudal, it gives off numerous short vertical branches, 77 above and 80 below the main line. These branches consist of true mucous canals with pores and with 2 rows of thin scales on each side; they are of various lengths, unbranched, and lie in a vertical plane, the lower branches extending half the distance to the anal fin and the upper branches half the distance to the dorsal fin. The lateral line proper is accompanied on each side by a narrow series of long thin scales.

The eye is located directly above the base of the mandible. The lower jaw is pointed and slightly the longer. The maxillary is attached in such a manner as to admit of considerable movement of the upper jaw. Each jaw has a single row of rather large compressed teeth which are rounded at the top. The teeth are very small at the tip of the jaw, but increase in size, posteriorly, to 12 millimeters in length; vomer and palatine somewhat roughened, but without teeth; opercle rounded with a very inconspicuous point posteriorly; preopercle toothed;

¹In our figure of this species the vertical branches of the lateral line are emphasized, and the true lateral line shows but three rows of scales whereas there should be six.

pectoral fins on median line of the body, their origin on a line with the origin of the ventrals and of the spinous dorsal, being midway between the tip of the snout and the base of the 20th dorsal spine; length of pectoral is 1.90 in head; ventral 4.10 in head; spinous dorsal long, and free from the soft dorsal, its anterior spine the longest, being 5 in head. The remaining spines are but slightly less in length until the 23rd spine is reached. The 24th to 26th are graduated. Longest ray of soft dorsal 4.5 in head; its origin midway between the origin of spinous dorsal and the end of the caudal vertebra. There are 9 free, distinct pinnules, with 1 additional pinnule attached by membrane to the soft dorsal. Origin of anal directly below the 7th ray of the soft dorsal; the length of anal rays equal to rays of dorsal. There are 8 free pinnules behind the anal fin with 1 additional pinnule attached to the fin. The origin of the anal is slightly nearer the end of the caudal vertebræ than to tip of ventrals. The caudal fin is falcate with the middle rays slightly projecting.

The caudal peduncle is strongly keeled; with the addition of 2 small oblique keels on base of caudal fin.

The head is naked; a narrow corslet of thin scales surrounds the anterior portion of the body and embraces the base of pectorals and of ventrals; a narrow line of scales along base of spinous dorsal; a rather wide area of long thin scales on the belly, extending back to the origin of the anal, this area being of greater width than the distance between the base of ventrals. These scales are very distinct, being about 8 millimeters in length by 1 millimeter in width.

Color in life, a beautiful steel-blue above, becoming lighter on sides and below; the dense scaled area of belly being fulvous; some beautiful dark blue vertical stripes on sides, which disappear within a few moments after the fish is taken from the water; the dorsal is dark blue; the caudal is bluish; the ventrals, pectorals, and anal are white, the tip of the anal being slightly shaded with gray; the head is colored similar to the body.

Type is No. 7253; length, 1.7 meters (64 inches); weight, 29.5 kilograms (65 pounds); caught off the coast of Leyte by Dean C. Worcester, August, 1911.

Named in honor of Governor-General W. Cameron Forbes in recognition of his interest in the development of the fisheries of the Philippine Islands.

Upon my first examination of this fish, I regarded it as being identical with the species called *Cubium sara* Benn., from the Loo Choo Islands, but after carefully looking up all the descrip-

tions and literature² relating to this species (now called *Cybium solanderi* Cuv. and Val.), I am convinced that this species is distinct.

The most striking features of *A. forbesi* are the peculiar, long thin scales on the belly and the branches of the lateral line, points of which I am sure the numerous careful naturalists who have examined *C. solanderi* (*C. sara*) would not have failed to mention in their descriptions. Also Jordan and Evermann described *A. solanderi* as having serrated teeth. The teeth of our specimen are apparently smooth. The above and several other points of differences, especially in the location of the fins, seem to make it necessary to describe our specimen as a distinct species.

² Bennett, in Beechey's Voyage Zool. (1849), 63, Pl. 20, fig. 2.

Cuvier and Valenciennes, Histoire Naturelle des Poissons (1831), 8, 141.

Gunther, Fische der Südsee (1876), 2, Taf. 94, Figs. A und B; Cat. Fishes Brit. Mus. (1860), 2, 373.

Doderlein, Grom de Sc. Nat. Ed. Ecom. (1872), 8.

Jordan and Evermann, Fishes of North and Middle America (1896), Part I, 876, Bull. U. S. Fish Comm. (1903), Pl. 1, 176.

ILLUSTRATION.

PLATE I.

Acanthocybium forbesi Seale. Forbes' Kingfish. (Drawing by Espinosa.)

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PLATE I. ACANTHOCYBIUM FORBESI Scale.

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(New names are printed in heavy-faced type; numbers in *italics* indicate synonyms or references of minor importance.)

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